

ANISOTROPIC DAMAGE OF A CARBON-SiC COMPOSITE UNDER OFF-AXIS LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The non-linear mechanical behaviour of an 2D Carbon SiC composite is investigated by means of an ultrasonic method which provides the necessary stiffness variations of the orthotropic material, inaccessible by classical strain measurements, required to identify anisotropic damage. The induced anisotropy depends on the loading direction. If a tensile solicitation in a fiber direction lead to stiffnesses decreases without any rotation of principal axes, a tensile solicitation in 45° from fiber direction creates microcracks with a predominant orientation that do not coincide with the elastic symmetry axes and induce a fully anisotropic elastic degradation.

Keywords: Ceramic matrix, Ultrasonic END, Micro-cracking, Damage, Anisotropy, symmetry degradation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic-matrix composites exhibit a non linear mechanical behaviour due to multiple matrix microcracking /1/. The purpose of the damage concept is to take into account this microscopic deterioration in the macroscopic constitutive law. In composite materials, the microcracks have preferential orientation and the damage variable depends on the direction of measurement /2/. Non linear analysis of such materials must consider this anisotropy by introducing a tensorial damage variable in the constitutive equations. For applications of continuum damage mechanics to composites /3, 4/, damage was introduced as an internal state variable whose tensorial nature depends on assumption about cracks geometry. An extensive review of the damage models has been given by Krajcinovic /5/. The main difficulties when dealing with anisotropic description of damage are to identify the introduced parameters.

The feasibility of the ultrasonic evaluation of damage has already been shown /6, 7/. The ultrasonic technique makes it possible to measure the stiffness tensor of an anisotropic material /8, 9, 10/. The association of an immersed interferometer with a tensile machine leads to the identification of the elastic tensor changes during a tensile test /11/.

The purpose of this paper is the macroscopic representation of the inelastic behaviour of a 2D Carbon-SiC composite material submitted to a tensile test in 45° from fiber direction. This off-axis solicitation creates microcracks with a predominant orientation that do not coincide with the elastic symmetry axes and induce a fully anisotropic elastic degradation.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material studied is a bi-directional Carbon-SiC composite prepared by S.E.P. It is fabricated from preforms built up from multiple layers of Carbon cloths. The SiC matrix was added by a chemical vapour infiltration process. Under tensile test, the composite presents a particular behaviour with a typical non linearity associated to the matrix micro-cracking since the strain-to-failure of the matrix is smaller than the fiber one. The loading-unloading cycles are showing that the non linearity consists in a decrease of the elastic stiffness. Two samples referred to as S0 and S45, in the form of plates measuring $190 \times 50 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$, are used in this study. Sample S0 is cutting out according to the cloths axes and S45 according to a 45° angle versus fibers axes.

The main principles and methods of ultrasonic NDE have been given by J. Roux /12/ for the evaluation of the elastic constants of anisotropic materials. The measurements made in the two accessible principal planes lead to the identification of seven coefficients of the stiffness tensor, namely: C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{12} , C_{66} for a propagation in the plane (1, 2), and C_{11} , C_{33} , C_{13} , C_{55} in the plane (1, 3). The two remaining coefficients C_{23} and C_{44} are identified by propagation in the non-principal plane (1, 45°) of orthotropic materials. For tetragonal material, this plane is a plane of symmetry and those two stiffnesses can be not measured independently /13/. The value of C_{44} is measured with contact transducers. The value of C_{23} is recovered in the plane (1, 45°).

The Carbon cloths are balanced weaves. So, the directions 2 and 3 are symmetrically equivalent. Certain stiffnesses are equal. The Carbon-SiC 2D composite presents a tetragonal symmetry with six independent stiffnesses. The stiffnesses of the sample S0 before load, in the coordinate axes placed on the cloths axes, Figure 1, and their 90 % confidence interval are:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= 19 \pm 2 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{22} &= 118 \pm 7 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{33} &= 123 \pm 4 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{12} &= 7.9 \pm 0.6 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{13} &= 7.7 \pm 0.3 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{23} &= 23 \pm 30 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{44} &= 23 \pm 2 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{55} &= 8.5 \pm 0.2 \text{ GPa} \\ C_{66} &= 9.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ GPa} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1. Coordinate axes.

3. STIFFNESS TENSOR CHANGE UNDER TENSILE LOADING IN FIBER DIRECTION

Sample S0 has been submitted to a tensile test in the direction 3. Figure 2 represents the evolution of the elastic constants versus applied stress for the Carbon-SiC 2D. We note an important loss of stiffness along the tensile axis (axis 3), from 123 GPa to 75 GPa. It is worth noting that the microcracking also has an important effect on shear moduli, and particularly on those relative to the planes that contain the loading direction, i.e. C_{44} and C_{55} . The damage level reached by the damage parameters associated to those shear moduli are similar to the one reached by C_{33} . The elastic symmetry, which was initially tetragonal, becomes increasingly orthorhombic.

The internal structure change, which occurs in certain materials under stress, affects their physical and mechanical properties. Degradation of one of those properties is an indirect measurement of damage. It is now commonly recognised that the change in elasticity is the correct measure of damage /5-14/. The values of the elastic compliances themselves can be taken as a characterisation of the state of damage of the material. The elasticity tensor can be written in an additive form /15/:

$$C = C_0 - C_c, \quad (1)$$

in terms of the stiffness tensor C_0 of the uncracked material and of the loss of stiffness C_c due to the microcracks. The variation of the stiffness tensor:

$$\omega = C_c = C_0 - C, \quad (2)$$

is selected as an internal variable representing the current state of the microcracking of the material. Like the initial elasticity tensor C_0 , the effective stiffness is a fourth rank symmetrical tensor, and the damage variable ω shows the same properties.

Figure 2. Variation of the stiffness tensor coefficients (GPa) and their 90 % relative confidence interval with the tensile stress in fibers direction 3, sample S0.

Traditionally, in phenomenological models based on the thermodynamics of continuous media, the damage parameter varies from zero for the initial state to the critical value $D=1$ at the failure of the volume element/16/. To this end it is necessary to normalise the components of the damage tensor to their thermodynamically admissible maximum values such that the elasticity tensor is still a positive defined operator /15/:

$$D_{ii} = 1 - \frac{C_{ij}}{C_{ii}^0}, \quad i = 1 \text{ to } 6, \quad (3)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}^0 - C_{ij}}{C_{ij}^0 + \text{Sign}(C_{ij}^0 - C_{ij}) \sqrt{C_{ii}^0 (1 - D_{ii}) C_{jj}^0 (1 - D_{jj})}}, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 6, i \neq j. \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) expresses the effect of both D_{ii} and D_{jj} damages of i and j directions upon the coupling coefficient C_{ij} of those two directions without prescribing that the changes of those off-diagonal elastic constants are directly proportional to the changes of diagonal elastic constants.

The variations of the stiffnesses C_{ij} at each level of stress give the evolution of the damage tensor components D_{ij} using the relations (3, 4). These variations, Figure 3, are different for different components and show clearly the anisotropy of the damage phenomenon. The cracks grow preferentially in the plane transverse to the loading direction since the damage D_{33} associated to the stiffness in the tensile axis 3 exhibits an important linear increase. It is worth noting that this micro-cracking has also an important effect on shear moduli and particularly on those relative to the planes that contain the loading direction (C_{44} and C_{55}). So, the only non zero components of the damage tensor are D_{33} , D_{44} and D_{55} . It is in line with the analytical predictions of the effective elasticity tensor of an solid which contains penny-shaped cracks normal to the axis 3 /17/.

Figure 3. Evolution of damage tensor coefficients with the tensile stress in fiber direction 3, sample S0.

4. STIFFNESS TENSOR CHANGE UNDER 45° OFF-AXIS TENSILE LOADING

The study of effects of an off-axis sollicitation is inspected on using the sample S45 cutting out according to a 45° angle versus fibers axes loading in this direction. Let R' ($1'$, $2'$, $3'$) be the coordinate system associated to the sample S45 and R (1 , 2 , 3) the coordinate axes associated to the fibers, Figure 4. Rotation of coordinate through an angle 45° about the $1 = 1'$ axis allows us to go from one coordinate system to another. The stiffnesses in the R' ($1'$, $2'$, $3'$) coordinate system are C_{ij}' .

Figure 4. R' ($1'$, $2'$, $3'$) coordinate system associated to the sample S45, R (1 , 2 , 3) the coordinate axes associated to the fibers.

Since the Carbon-SiC 2D composite presents a tetragonal symmetry, this class of symmetry is retained in the R' (1', 2', 3') coordinate system and the stiffness matrix is:

$$[C'] = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}' & C_{12}' & C_{13}' & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12}' & C_{22}' & C_{23}' & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13}' & C_{23}' & C_{33}' & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44}' & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55}' & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66}' \end{bmatrix}$$

with: $C_{22}' = C_{33}' \quad C_{66}' = C_{55}' \quad C_{12}' = C_{13}'$

On using the coordinate transformation matrix M, the stiffness matrix in the R (1, 2, 3) coordinate system becomes /18/:

$$[C] = [M][C'] [M]^t = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & C_{34} & 0 & 0 \\ C_{14} & C_{24} & C_{34} & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & C_{56} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{56} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= C_{11}' & C_{22} &= C_{33}' = \frac{1}{4}(C_{33}' + C_{22}') + C_{44}' + \frac{C_{23}'}{2} \\ C_{44} &= \frac{1}{4}(C_{22}' + C_{33}') - \frac{C_{23}'}{2} & C_{66} &= C_{55}' = \frac{1}{2}(C_{66}' + C_{55}') \\ C_{12} &= C_{13}' = \frac{1}{2}(C_{12}' + C_{13}') & C_{23} &= \frac{1}{4}(C_{22}' + C_{33}') + \frac{C_{23}'}{2} - C_{44}' \\ C_{14} &= \frac{1}{2}(C_{12}' - C_{13}') & C_{24} &= C_{34}' = \frac{1}{4}(C_{33}' - C_{22}') & C_{56} &= \frac{1}{2}(C_{55}' - C_{66}') \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

For the sample S45 studied, the stiffnesses before load measured in the R' (1', 2', 3') coordinate system are shown in Tab. 1. The tetragonal symmetry is quite checked. So, the tensile-shear coupling coefficients C₁₄, C₂₄, C₃₄ and C₅₆ in the (1, 2, 3) coordinate axes, calculated from equation (5), are equal to zero. The stiffnesses C_{ij} calculated from equation (5) are equal to those measured in the plane (1, 2) of the (1, 2, 3) coordinate axes, Tab. 1.

Table 1. Stiffness coefficients (in GPa) and associated 90 % confidence interval of the S45 sample.

C _{ij} ' measured in R' (1', 2', 3')	C _{ij} calculated in R (1, 2, 3)	C _{ij} measured in plane (1, 2)
C ₁₁ ' = 17 ± 1	C ₁₁ = 17 ± 1	C ₁₁ = 17 ± 1
C ₂₂ ' = 71 ± 4	C ₂₂ = C ₃₃ = 99 ± 8	C ₂₂ = 85 ± 8
C ₃₃ ' = 65 ± 3	C ₆₆ = C ₅₅ = 11 ± 0.2	C ₆₆ = 10.5 ± 0.3
C ₆₆ ' = 11 ± 0.1	C ₄₄ = 19 ± 5	
C ₅₅ ' = 10.8 ± 0.3	C ₁₂ = C ₁₃ = 2.4 ± 0.4	C ₁₂ = 2.3 ± 1
C ₄₄ ' = 50 ± 2	C ₂₃ = -1 ± 8	
C ₁₂ ' = 2.5 ± 0.4	C ₁₄ = 0.1 ± 0.4 ≈ 0	
C ₁₃ ' = 2.3 ± 0.4	C ₂₄ = C ₃₄ = -1.5 ± 2 ≈ 0	
C ₂₃ ' = 30 ± 7	C ₅₆ = -0.1 ± 0.2 ≈ 0	

Sample S45 has been submitted to an off-axis tensile test in the direction 3'. Figure 5 represents the variation of the elastic constants versus the σ₃' applied stress measured with the hypothesis required by the ultrasonic technique that the material keeps its orthorhombic symmetry in the R' (1', 2', 3') coordinate system. The stiffness C₃₃' along the tensile axis strongly decreases. The degradation affects also the shear moduli C₄₄', C₅₅' et C₆₆'. On the other hand, C₂₂' is essentially constant. The cracks grow preferentially in the plane transverse to the loading direction 3'. The elastic symmetry, which was initially tetragonal, becomes increasingly orthorhombic in the (1', 2', 3') coordinate axes.

Figure 5. Variation of the stiffness tensor coefficients (GPa) and their 90 % relative confidence interval in the R' (1', 2', 3') coordinate system, sample S45 submitted to an 45° off-axis tensile test.

The loss of the tetragonal symmetry, since C_{33}' is no more equal to C_{22}' , in the R' (1', 2', 3') coordinate system, induces that the material becomes monoclinic, with 13 independents constants, in the (1, 2, 3) coordinate axes. For the particular choose of rotation through an angle 45°, there are nine independents stiffnesses; C_{11} , $C_{22} = C_{33}$, $C_{55} = C_{66}$, C_{44} , $C_{12} = C_{13}$, C_{23} , $C_{14} = C_{34}$ and C_{56} .

C_{12}' remain close to C_{13}' . Similarly, the variation of C_{55}' is quite the same that C_{66}' one. Consequently, the values of C_{14} and C_{56} remain weak. On the other hand, the previously zero tensile-shear coupling coefficients C_{24} and C_{34} have now become non zero.

The variations of the stiffnesses C_{ij} in the (1, 2, 3) coordinate axes calculated from equation (5) at each level of stress give the evolution of the damage tensor components D_{ij} in this coordinate system using the relations (3, 4), Figure 6. The damage parameters D_{22} and D_{33} are equal since the coordinate transformation gives $C_{22} = C_{33}$ for any stress level. It is in line with the fact that the directions 2 and 3 are submitted at the same tensile stress $\sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = \sigma_3 / \sqrt{2}$. The damages of the shear planes are consequent because of the superposition of the damage induced by the tensile stresses σ_2 and σ_3 and the shear stress $\sigma_4 = \sigma_{23} = 0.5 \sigma_3$.

The more noteworthy effect of the off-axis tensile sollicitation in the direction 3' is that the non-diagonals damage parameters D_{24} and D_{34} exhibit an increase of 0.5. This increase is due to the loss of the orthorhombic symmetry in the R(1, 2, 3) coordinate system associated to the fibbers. The off-axis tensile stress initiates microcracks that grow preferentially in the plane transverse to the loading direction 3'. The predominant orientation of those cracks does not coincide with the fibbers axes and induces a fully anisotropic elastic degradation.

Figure 6. Evolution of damage tensor coefficients calculated in the R (1, 2, 3) coordinate system, sample S45 submitted to an 45° off-axis tensile test.

5. CONCLUSION

The behaviour of matrix ceramic composites is strongly influenced by nucleation and growth of microcracks. This deterioration is measured, at the macroscopic scale, by the changes of the material's stiffnesses. Since cracks have overriding propagation directions, the effect is highly anisotropic and the variations of the whole stiffness tensor must be studied. Damage is defined as the change of the elasticity tensor. This fourth rank symmetrical tensor is selected as the internal variable representing the current state of the material degradation. The components of this tensor can be measured, have a clearly identifiable physical meaning and form a finite set of data. No particular elastic symmetries need to be assumed and fully anisotropic elastic degradation can be accounted for. If the directions of cracks growth are in respect with the bi-directional texture of the composite, the material keeps its orthorhombic symmetry during the degradation process. It is the case when the composite is submitted to a tensile test in fiber direction. A tensile solicitation in 45° from fiber direction creates microcracks with a predominant orientation that do not coincide with the fibers axes and induce a fully anisotropic elastic degradation. For this kind of degradation, the material effectively keeps its orthorhombic symmetry but the principal axes, which remain mutually orthogonal, change their direction under load.

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